

COMMON DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED IN TEACHING SPEAKING COMPETENCIES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO LEARNERS

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Аннотация: Коммуникативная методика преподавания иностранных языков признана наиболее эффективной во всем мире, и на сегодняшний день многие преподаватели ВУЗов работают на ее основе. В основе коммуникативной методики лежит изучение языка через ситуации общения.

Это соединение традиционного и интенсивного методов, но с рядом своих особенностей. Данный метод помогает преодолеть языковой барьер, избавляет человека от боязни говорить на чужом языке. На занятиях студенты имеют возможность использовать язык в реальных жизненных ситуациях.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативная методика, преподавание французского языка, традиционный и интенсивный метод, языковой барьер.

Abstract: The communicative methodology of teaching foreign languages is recognized as the most effective all over the world, and today many university teachers work on its basis. The basis of the communicative methodology is the study of language through communication situations.

This is a combination of traditional and intensive methods, but with a number of its own features. This method helps to overcome the language barrier, relieves a person from the fear of speaking a foreign language. In the classroom, students have the opportunity to use the language in real life situations.

Keywords: communicative methodology, teaching French, traditional and intensive method, language barrier.

The communicative method develops all language skills: from oral and written speech to reading and listening. Grammar is studied in the process of communicating in a language: the student first learns and remembers words, expressions, language formulas and only then begins to understand what they represent in the sense of grammar. Classes are held in a relaxed atmosphere. Communication takes place only in a foreign language.

New rules, words are explained by the teacher only with the help of familiar vocabulary, grammatical constructions, gestures, facial expressions, drawings and other visual aids.

Role-playing and dramatization are very effective at the initial stage of training. Dramatization is a representation in the form of scenes, fairy tales, short stories, as

well as plot paintings. Everyday situations are played out: acquaintance, choosing a travel route, congratulations, shopping, and so on.

The game provides an emotional impact on language learners, activates the reserve capabilities of a person. It facilitates the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities, creates conditions for the active mental activity of its participants. All its participants are equal, even the weakest are not shy due to a sense of equality. If the participant of the role-playing game does not know a word, he always has the opportunity to replace it with any other.

Also, with the help of a role-playing game, students learn to instantly come up with synonyms or rearrange sentences in a very short time, depending on how the conversation develops. The participants of the game can change and accept any images to their taste and build their conversation about it.

The process of learning a language using a communicative method is similar to how we learned our native language in childhood. The formation of skills goes through several stages:

- 1) mastering standard skills;
- 2) automation of their application;
- 3) development of skills in free communication situations.

Studying according to the communicative method, the goal of each lesson is for the student to develop a stable reflex that a certain "meaning" in French sounds like this, and so that, if necessary, in real life, he can reproduce this "meaning" independently. The question of which grammatical structures were used for this is important, but is not an end in itself.

French courses published by Hachette, Clé International are focused on the development of not only language knowledge, but also creativity and the general outlook of the student. The language is very closely intertwined with the cultural characteristics of the country, therefore, the courses certainly include a country-specific aspect.

French methods have a number of distinctive features. Most of them are developed based on the integration of traditional and modern teaching methods. Differentiation by age groups and a multi-level approach make it possible to develop an individual human personality, affect its worldview, value system, self-identification, and ability to think. At the forefront is the now popular individual approach. Without exception, all French methods are aimed at developing four language skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening. At the same time, great emphasis is placed on the use of audio, video and interactive resources. Due to the variety of methodological techniques, among which one of the leading places is occupied by language technologies that contribute to the formation of skills necessary for a person in modern business life. The undeniable advantages of French developers

are the preparation of a course based on authentic material, great attention to stylistics, the desire to teach "situational" and "live" French through "life" examples of semi-real characters.

The communicative technique has been used all over the world for many decades, especially in Europe. The communicative approach of teaching is an approach that emphasizes communication and interaction with each other. This is exactly what is the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language.

when studying one or several foreign languages, a student is in a multicultural space, gets involved in civilization, history, and other spheres of life of the country of the language being studied, which has a positive effect on his horizons. When organizing the process of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to highlight the primary, most important information of a country-specific nature and its skillful, methodically motivated actualization in the language material being studied.

An important argument in favor of dividing teaching methods into three subtypes is the status of the French language in modern Europe, which is characterized by heterogeneity of position and is characterized by varying degrees of “dissimilarity” to the language of France. The scope of functions performed by the French language in European countries is also different.

The national doctrine of education in Ukraine among the most important tasks involves the formation of a high language culture of students, improving the language culture of citizens. In this regard, the development of new approaches to teaching a foreign language seems to be an urgent problem of a pedagogical university. The inclusion of Ukraine in the Bologna process requires a significant reorganization of the educational process in the context of the recommendations of the Council of Europe in the field of language policy. Despite the unstoppable development of philological and pedagogical thought, the content of education, the amount of hours of the curriculum allocated for the professional training of a practical teacher do not provide an appropriate level of professionalism: language competence, knowledge of modern methods of teaching French and mechanisms of psychological and pedagogical influence on students.

Modern trends in teaching foreign languages should be accompanied by radical changes in the methodological paradigm. In connection with the concept adopted by the Council of Europe on the key types of competence that should be prioritized in the formation of general educational strategies, when teaching French at a pedagogical university, it is necessary to remember that the indirect purpose of this process is related to the formation, in the future, of the communicative qualities of secondary school students, their ability to communicate in society, perform various social and communicative roles, to lead an active lifestyle using the latest technologies in the conditions of European and world integration. In other words,

regardless of the age and categories of students, the modern methodology must meet high requirements related not only to the formation of speech and communicative, but also social competence.

The teaching of the French language should be integrated into the process of forming the methodological skills of the future teacher. One of the positive aspects on the way to the formation of a new system of teaching French in a pedagogical university should be considered teaching a cycle of disciplines of practical methodology exclusively in French.

Another fundamental milestone of teacher training is the formation of his pedagogical skills. After all, it is pedagogical skill that enables the teacher to effectively guide any educational activity, influence the course of thoughts and subsequent speech messages created by students

Registration of students' documentation on pedagogical practice in a foreign language should become the norm. “Certification systems and assessment of students' language achievements”, “Ways of developing textbooks and teaching aids in the French language”, “The conceptual basis for creating educational and didactic materials for French lessons at different stages of learning” - this is not the whole list of educational modules that will bring practical benefits to future foreign language teachers in modern society.

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